

Spectroscopic, Thermodynamic, Electronic, HOMO-LUMO, MEP and NLO Analyses of 3-(Benzyl)-4-(3-Acetoxy-4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one

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Abstract

In this work, a triazole derivative that is commonly employed in industry, healthcare, particularly the pharmaceutical sector, was theoretically analyzed. The spectroscopic, electronic, thermodynamic, HOMO-LUMO, MEP and NLO properties of molecule were calculated. The molecule optimized with 6-311G(d,p) basis set and DFT(B3LYP) method. The structural properties such as dipole moment (μ), the total energy, electronic properties (electron affinity, molecular softness, ionization potential, molecular hardness and electronegativity), thermodynamic of molecule were determined. The infrared (FT-IR) vibrational data of molecule were determined with Veda 4 software set. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR calculations spectral data were obtained using the GIAO approach in the same basis set and than chemical shift values were compared with experimental data in literature. Also, the surface map such as MEP were obtained and thus, the electrophilic and nucleophilic moieties were shown on the compound. The nonlinear optical properties (NLO) were investigated and the results were evaluated according to the urea reference. Finally, the spectral and structural data of 1,2,4-triazole derivative compound were obtained and assessed in this theoretical study.

Keywords: B3LYP, DFT, MEP, NLO.

3-(Benzil)-4-(3-Asetoksi-4-metoksibenzilidenamino)-4,5-dihidro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5'in Spektroskopik, Termodinamik, Elektronik, HOMO-LUMO, MEP ve NLO Analizleri

Özet

Bu çalışmada endüstride, sağlık sektöründe ve özellikle ilaç sektöründe yaygın olarak kullanılan bir triazol türevinin teorik analizi yapılmıştır. Molekülün spektroskopik, elektronik, termodinamik, HOMO-LUMO, MEP ve NLO özellikleri hesaplanmıştır. Molekül 6-311G(d,p) temel seti ve DFT(B3LYP) yöntemi ile optimize edilmiştir. Molekülün dipol momenti (μ), toplam enerjisi, elektronik özellikleri (elektron ilgisi, moleküler yumuşaklık, iyonlaşma potansiyeli, moleküler sertlik ve elektronegatiflik), termodinamik gibi yapısal özellikleri belirlenmiştir. Molekülün kızılötesi (FT-IR) titreşim verileri Veda 4 yazılım seti ile belirlenmiştir. ¹H ve ¹³C NMR hesaplamalarının spektral verileri aynı temel sette GIAO yaklaşımı kullanılarak elde edildi ve ardından kimyasal kayma değerleri literatürdeki deneysel verilerle karşılaştırılmıştır. Ayrıca MEP gibi yüzey haritası elde edilmiş ve böylece bileşiğin elektrofilik ve nükleofilik kısımları gösterilmiştir. Doğrusal olmayan optik özellikler (NLO) araştırıldı ve sonuçlar üre referansına göre değerlendirilmiştir. Bu teorik çalışmada son olarak 1,2,4-triazol türevi bileşiğinin spektral ve yapısal verileri elde edilmiş ve değerlendirilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: B3LYP, DFT, MEP, NLO.

1. Introduction

Triazoles including three nitro atoms are five-membered heteroaromatic compounds. This properties of allows easy synthesis of new triazole derivatives. The triazole derivatives have wide usage areas in organic chemistry, pharmacology especially drug designe. Many studies on the evaluation of the biological of the triazoles have shown that the triazole compounds exhibit anti-fungal (Peyton et al, 2015; Shalini et al., 2011; Koltin & Hitchcock, 1997), anti-oksident (Yüksek et al., 2006; Kotan, 2021), anti-bacterial (Boy et al., 202; Al-Radadi et al., 2020), anti-cancer (Kamal et al., 2008), anti-tuberculos (Zhang et al., 2017), anti-HIV (Li et al., 2013) properties. The compound whose theoretical properties were investigated in this study is a triazole Schiff Base. The Schiff Baze compounds containe azomethine grup (-C=N-) and generally obtaine by the reaction of aldehyde or ketone with primary amine (Berhanu et al., 2019). The Schiff Bases which have important uses fields as organic chemistry, analitycal chemistry, metal chemistry have played effective role in coordination chemistry and bioinorganic chemistry (Uddin et al., 2020). Many study deal with the Schiff Bazes ligands and their complexes have reported that these compounds show anti-cancer (Zafar et al., 2021), anti-fungal (Chohan et al., 2010), anti-microbiyal (Manap, 2020) properties. In addition , these compounds are included in the structure of drugs used in the treatment of many diseases in medicine (Uddin et al., 2020). The Gaussian 09W software was used to do all theoretical calculations for the focus on chemical. (Frisch et al., 2009). The DFT approach was used to optimize the molecule (Wolinski et al 1990; Frisch et al., 2009). The theoretical calculations were performed by using optimized molecule with DFT(B3LYP)/6-311G(d,p) (Boy et al., 2022). The experimental results were acquired from the literature (Bahçeci et al., 2017). Tables and graphs were used to compare and illustrate these results.

2. Result And Discussion

2.1. Computational details

The Gaussian 09W packet software (Frisch et al.,2009) was used to compute all quantum chemical calculations. The GaussView application was used to sketch the molecule Figure 1 depicts the geometric structure and formula that has been optimized. It is the molecule's most stable three-dimensional structure.

Figure 1. The Gaussview structure of the molecule.

2.2. ¹H-NMR calculations

In comparison to experimental values, the theoretical ¹H-Nükleer magnetic rezonans chemical shift values were computed in gaseous and solvent (DMSO) environments and are displayed in Table 1. The "GIAO" method (Wolinski, 1990) was used to calculate the proton NMR chemical shift values. The regression analyses were performed, and graphs were created.

Table 1. ¹H/ ¹³C-NMR(DMSO) isotropic chemical shifts (δ /ppm)

Atoms	Experimental	DFT	Differ/6-311G(d,p)
H20	11.9	7.46	4.44
H21	9.58	9.98	-0.40
H22	7.65	8.28	-0.63
H23	7.55	7.43	0.12
H24	7.17	7.18	-0.01
H25	3.85	3.40	0.45
H26	3.85	3.96	-0.11
H27	3.85	4.04	-0.19

H28	2.3	2.48	-0.18
H29	2.3	2.38	-0.08
H30	2.3	1.75	0.55
H31	4.05	4.05	0.00
H32	4.05	3.89	0.16
H33	7.3	7.73	-0.43
H34	7.2	7.58	-0.38
H35	7.27	7.44	-0.17
H36	7.2	7.52	-0.32
H37	7.3	7.62	-0.32

2.3. Regression Analysis

There is such a link between the compound's R^2 -values. B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) (DMSO): ^1H : 0.8303, as shown in Figure 2. Theoretical and experimental proton chemical shifts ratios between R2 linear correlations were observed.

Figure 2. The ^1H -NMR correlation graph

2.4. The IR Analysis

The theoretical scale values and IR values were calculated using the Veda 4F software (Jamroz et al., 2004). The harmonic vibrational frequency readings were scaled for the B3LYP level using 0.9688. (Merrick et al., 2007). In the data, a positive frequency was discovered. In accordance with DFT method, IR spectrums were drawn using the measured data. Theoretical and empirically acquired IR values were compared, and their values coincided.

Table 3. Same IR vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1})

vibrational frequencies	Experimental IR	Scaled B3LYP
ν (NH)	3186	3565
ν (C=O)	1765, 1705	1806-1750
ν (C=N)	1604-1590	1613, 1593
ν (COO)	1276	1279

Figure 3. Experimental Theoretical IR spectrum

2.5. The mulliken charge calculation

With the use of the 6-311G(d,p) basis set and the "B3LYP" approach, the molecule's mulliken charge values were computed. The mulliken atomic charges (Mulliken, 1955) of the electronegative N38-N41 atoms in the molecule were estimated as negative, while the mulliken charges of all protons in the molecule were computed as positive, according to the findings of the calculations with 6-311G(d,p). In addition, it was discovered that "C1, C2, C3, C7 and C8" atoms had positive mulliken charge values whereas other carbon atoms had negative values. This is due to the presence of one electronegative oxygen atom and two electronegative nitrogen atoms next to the C1, C2, and C3 atoms, respectively.

Table 6. The calculated all atomic charges

	B3LYP		B3LYP
C1	0.357	H24	0.099
C2	3.535	H25	0.101
C3	0.128	H26	0.120
C4	-0.168	H27	0.115
C5	-0.001	H28	0.138
C6	-0.086	H29	0.136
C7	0.168	H30	0.141
C8	0.161	H31	0.152
C9	-0.004	H32	0.138
C10	-0.114	H33	0.086
C11	0.307	H34	0.093
C12	-0.296	H35	0.095
C13	-0.161	H36	0.096
C14	-0.122	H37	0.100
C15	-0.059	N38	-0.216
C16	-0.097	N39	-0.312
C17	-0.087	N40	-0.383
C18	-0.091	N41	-0.205
C19	-0.038	O42	-0.388
H20	0.251	O43	-0.367
H21	0.142	O44	-0.371
H22	0.112	O45	-0.304
H23	0.102		

Figure 4. The calculated mulliken charges

2.6. FMO's Calculations

Quantum chemical characteristics, for example, E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} , and ΔE are useful indicators of a chemical's reactivity. The zone of reactivity at a molecule's border is indicated by the electron density of the molecule. Using DFT/6-311G(d,p), the frontier electron density was determined (Fukui et al., 1952) The excitation energy is calculated as the difference between the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) and the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO). The stability of molecules is represented by this energy gap. In a molecule, LUMO stands for an electron acceptor and HOMO for an electron donor (Amudha et al., 2022)

Figure 4. HOMO-LUMO energy and ΔE

Table 7. The calculated electronic data

	Hatree	ev	kcal/mol	KJ/mol
LUMO	-0,0658	-1,79046	-41,2897	-172,758
HOMO	-0,227	-6,17683	-142,443	-595,989
A Electron Affinity	0,0658	1,79046	41,2897	172,758
I Ionization Potential	0,227	6,17683	142,443	595,989
ΔE Energy gap	0,1612	4,38636	101,153	423,231
χ electronegativity	0,1464	3,98365	91,8664	384,373
Pi chemical potential	-0,1464	-3,98365	-91,8664	-384,373

ω	electrophilic index	0,000863748	0,0235	0,542	2,26777
IP	Nucleophilic index	-0,01179984	-0,32108	-7,40443	-30,9805
S	molecular softness	12,4069	337,602	7785,4	32574,4
η	molecular hardness	0,0806	2,19318	50,5767	211,615

Figure 5. The MEP

2.7. Non-Linear Optic Analysis (NLO)

Numerous technologies, including optical computers, dynamic image processing, optical switches, dye lasers, telecommunication devices, and optical disks, have benefited greatly from the development of nonlinear optical (NLO) materials. As a result, efforts are being made to mimic several NLO-phores, including inorganic and organic semiconductors, naturally occurring and artificial nanomaterials, polymers and dyes (Fonseca et al., 2018; Halasyamani et al., 2017; Hussain et al., 2020; Deb et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2018). NLO parameters such as anisotropy of polarizability ($\Delta\alpha$), average linear polarizability (α), first hyperpolarizability (β_{total}), the total static dipole moment (μ) were determined with DFT_{B3LYP}.

Polarizability " $\alpha_{xx}, \alpha_{xy}, \alpha_{yy}, \alpha_{xz}, \alpha_{yz}, \alpha_{zz}$ " = 347.2495516; 34.860844; 263.7561871; 1.4105161; 7.1858105; 165.1231724 and HyperPolar " $\beta_{xxx}, \beta_{xxy}, \beta_{xyy}, \beta_{yyy}, \beta_{xxz}, \beta_{xyz}, \beta_{yyz}, \beta_{xzz}, \beta_{yzz}, \beta_{zzz}$ " = -139.2929225; 1.2451982; 33.584864; 175.4535599; 42.7543767; -36.4465889; -32.4295204; 15.8601426; 54.6213466; -29.2101699 values, respectively were obtained. These values using assigned theoretical results are α_{total} : 38.341×10^{-24} esu, $\Delta\alpha$: 23.402×10^{-24} esu and β^0 : 20.83×10^{-31} esu. The primary reference material for NLO qualities is the urea molecule. The NLO parameters for urea refereans according to literature are α_{total} : $5.07643717 \times 10^{-24}$ esu, $\Delta\alpha$: $2.13568262 \times 10^{-24}$ esu and β^0 : $7.2228469891 \times 10^{-31}$ esu (Kotan et al., 2022). The NLO values were 7.6, 11, and 2.8 times more than urea as compared to the reference material.

Table 8. The the average polarizability α_{total} (10^{-24} esu), total energy E_{total} (Hartree), the electric dipole moment μ (Debye) and first hyperpolarizability β_{total} (10^{-31} esu) of molecule

	B3LYP
E_{total}	-1255.05045284
μ_x	0.8805
μ_y	-2.3122
μ_z	2.0732
μ_{Total}	3.2280
α_{xx}	347.2495516
α_{xy}	34.860844
α_{yy}	263.7561871
α_{xz}	1.4105161
α_{yz}	7.1858105
α_{zz}	165.1231724
α_{total}	38.341×10^{-24} esu
$\Delta\alpha$	23.402×10^{-24} esu
β_{xxx}	-139.2929225
β_{xxy}	1.2451982
β_{xyy}	33.584864

β_{yyy}	175.4535599
β_{xxz}	42.7543767
β_{xyz}	-36.4465889
β_{yyz}	-32.4295204
β_{xzz}	15.8601426
β_{yzz}	54.6213466
β_{zzz}	-29.2101699
β_{total}	20.83 x10 ⁻³¹ esu

2.8. Thermodynamics parameters

Thermodynamic parameters were estimated using B3LYP functionals in the DFT technique at 298.150 K and 1 atm pressure using the 6-311G(d,p) basis.

Table 10. The calculated thermodynamics parameters of the molecule

Rotational temperatures (Kelvin) DFT	
A	0.01477
B	0.00423
C	0.00348
Rotational constants (GHZ)	
A	0.30786
B	0.08815
C	0.07245
Thermal Energies E(kcal/mol)	
Translational	0.889
Rotational	0.889
Vibrational	232.220
Total	233.997
Thermal Capacity CV(cal/mol-K)	
Translational	2.981
Rotational	2.981
Vibrational	85.947
Total	91.908
Entropy S(cal/mol-K)	
Translational	43.587
Rotational	36.345
Vibrational	99.280
Total	179.212
Zero-point correction (Hartree/Particle)	0.348073
Thermal correction to Energy	0.372898
Thermal correction to Enthalpy	0.373842
Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy	0.288693
Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies	-1254.702380
Sum of electronic and thermal Energies	-1254.677555
Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies	-1254.676610
Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies	-1254.761760
Zero-point vibrational energy (Kcal/mol)	218.41889

3. Conclusion

Some theoretical calculations of the target molecule were made. By comparing the proton nmr data with the experimental one, regression graphs were created. As a result, it was seen that there was a deviation in the ¹H-NMR because of the acidic proton (N-H). In addition, the reactivity of the molecule was calculated from the HOMO-LUMO energy difference and many electronic parameters were calculated using this difference. MEP surface map was created and as a result electrophile and nucleophile atoms were determined. Mulliken load values were found. The estimated IR vibration frequency values were compared to the experimental results and their were in agreement with each other.

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